

Metadata stewardship in nanosafety research X: approaches to improve completeness of structured metadata reporting

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Abstract

Main ideas of paper:

- 1) 8 years after the first FAIR workshop and 6 years after publication of the FAIR principles: tools for data management is continuously improving
- 2) General specialised databases vs. general purpose data repositories
- 3) Not one size fits all - harmonised but flexible
- 4) Different projects and the associated databases concentrated on different aspects to improve metadata quality
- 5) Can only work for defined environments, i.e. defined type of data. However, the diversity of science seen even in relatively small fields like nanosafety research prohibits the development of specific solutions for each data type.
- 6) Combining the advantages of homogeneity of specialized databases and the flexibility of multi-purpose databases is only possible if the challenge of defining (meta)data completeness is handled back to the scientific community and we do not expect that it is solved by data curators or managers.
- 7) However, the existing databases can still be used to guide this process and finally will provide the tooling to create such interoperable datasets.

Idea of general outline:

- 1) History (NANoREG, ISATAB-nano)
- 2) Increased requirements due to complexity and diversity of nanomaterials (CODATA UDS)
- 3) Increased requirements due to complex environments and nanomaterial fate (NIKC, NanoFASE)
- 4) Increased requirements due to new methodology (experimental and in silico, MODA/CHADA)
- 5) Solution 1: Learning from other projects and improving existing standards (ASINA, SBYNA, others?)
- 6) Solution 2: Highly structured metadata coverage to guide data providers with the example of protocols (ACEnano)
- 7) Solution 3: Linking data sources to provide holistic view (NanoCommons KB and perhaps with proposed extensions to also include outside protocol/SOP, MODA/CHADA/QMRF repositories)
- 8) Solution 4: Restructuring of data for specific applications (NanoPharos, JAQPOT, others?)

Data concepts to be covered:

- 1) NANoREG
- 2) VAMAS-CoData UDS
- 3) NIKC/NanoFASE + NanoCommons Knowledge warehouse
- 4) SmartNanoTox/NanoSolveIT
- 5) ASINA / SBYNA?
- 6) ACEnano - protocols as metadata
- 7) NanoCommons - Semantic integration and material focus
- 8) NanoPharos / Jaqpot

What we probably need:

1. Clear distinction between data point and data set management

2. Clear distinction between data provider and data user viewpoints
3. Related to this: SQL vs noSQL databases

1. Introduction

In the past years and especially since the introduction of the concept of data FAIRness (derived from the FAIR principles with FAIR standing for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), data management has again become a major topic not only discussed in circles normally associated with it like database developers and managers or data curators []. This can be attributed to two major societal and political trends forcing the scientific community to rethink their standard practices. 1) There is an increasing skepticism about the trustworthiness of scientific results in the general public towards science, associated with words like “fake news” and “alternative facts”, but also within the scientific community resulting in the announcement of a reproducibility crisis []. Providing the data and the evidence extractable from it in a more comprehensive, open and easily accessible manner will not be able to restore full confidence in science but will be supportive to provide the best arguments, which can be evaluated and reproduced by others. 2) The valid motion that maximum benefit needs to be extracted from public research investments has resulted in funding agencies, publishers and governmental agencies demanding the integration of more and more thorough data management and stewardship for making data reuse possible. Especially in the field of chemical and nanomaterial safety assessment, the societal pressure to reduce, refine and replace animal testing, collectively called the 3Rs, has inspired the development on many new methods, both *in vitro* and *in silico*. These, because of their currently still missing standardisation and complete validation, are especially demanding with respect to the information accompanying the data needed for trusted reuse or even primary use in regulatory reporting.

In the first part of this series of papers [], we described how the practical implementation of high-quality data management can be facilitated by a deeper understanding of what metadata is, and how to capture it, leading to the definition of clear roles and responsibilities across the complete data lifecycle. The main goal of the paper was to make clear that good data management is not a goal in itself done to please funding agencies or an anonymous reuser but that it is a central part of knowledge discovery and innovation providing benefits to but also requiring commitment from everyone. It is also important to mention that the possible benefits are not depending on the setting, in which the data is produced and used, and its size since data sharing and reuse happens at the individual level (using information from earlier work to design new studies) or individual groups up to international, multi-partner projects. Most of the time, we focus on the latter since here many different existing approaches have to be brought together but it is also where funding institutions have the most influence to enforce open data and open science approaches. Big projects also often include specific groups for data management and for developing database solutions made specifically for the projects but ultimately meant to become standard public data resources. An immense amount of expertise and know-how is generated in these activities especially when solutions are handed over from one project to the next and constantly improved over time in this way. In this paper, we describe some best-practice examples and analyse the specific implementations of databases, data warehouses and guidance documents to extract features and learnings optimally addressing challenges in managing nanosafety data. We then discuss how these features might be combined and potentially also separated from a specific database solution to be able to support the different data lifecycle stages with specific tools to collect, curate and manage the on the

fly and share it in an already harmonised and interoperable way with downstream stages including analysis, modelling and reuse.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Term definitions

Before we start to present the nanosafety-specific solutions, some data management and more general terminology will be discussed here. This is not meant to be seen as a part of data management or data science training but because we think that they might be helpful to classify different data management concepts and their implementation and also approach the topic from different angles, which can be associated to specific stakeholder groups like data providers and data users.

The first way to separate data approaches is if they focus on individual data points or on datasets. Even if this might seem to be a strange classification at first, since datasets are constructed out of data points, it will be used here to show that different applications and stakeholder groups require different representations of the data. As a dataset, we define here a set of data points, which are grouped together for a specific purpose. This can be to be able to present all the data and results from one specific study performed at one point in time. Many data curation templates described below are following this concept since they were designed to support experimentalists, working on a study, to prepare the data for upload to a database including all relevant data for this study. Other datasets can be created from existing data e.g. to be used as input for nanoinformatics approaches and to train *in silico* models. These can be stored to document the model development and, thus, can also be associated with a very specific purpose. However, such datasets generated for data reuse have already some links to the data point focused viewpoint. Before the data points are combined with the dataset, they have to be collected from potentially different sources. This might be the primary literature but also databases, which collect information using a data model organised specific search functionality. For example, data can be organised to provide all available information for a (nano)material, cell system, assay or any other object of interest. The user of such data collections would then pick independent data points to create a dataset special to their intended use. Before such a use case is applied, the data points can be seen as independent since they can be combined in many different ways to many different datasets. It is clear that each of these points has to be supported by (meta)data on where it comes from and how it was created and thus, there has to be a dataset describing the original study associated with it. However, this additional information is only of secondary interest to the user, which is why we also called it here (meta)data. Roughly speaking, we could say that the dataset focus is better suited to represent the data generator needs while the data point focus is allowing a multitude of data reuse cases.

A second way to classify concepts is to distinguish relational from non-relational database systems, often also referred to as SQL vs. noSQL databases. Even if these are specific implementations of databases, they are also related to the discussion in the previous paragraph.

- Short description of these types and their differences along the lines of https://aws.amazon.com/nosql/?nc1=h_ls
- Reasons why noSQL databases have increased popularity since the mid to late 2000s
- Relation to specific to general-purpose databases as well as allowing storage of units of data (datasets focus), which can then be rearranged according to the use cases (data point focus)

- Hypothesis: noSQL is moving annotation of data from database system to data provider/data curation template and thus, allows earlier, database independent collection of data.
- Benefit: Data does not have to be prepared for a specific project or database.

2.2 OECD endpoints

The complex nature and the unique properties of nanomaterials requires a thorough characterization of the material going into the experiment investigating their safeness to be able to clearly identify it and the state it is in and separate it from other similar materials, which still might show very different properties and behaviors. Examples of such complexity have been given in the first paper of this series [] and while presenting the first version of a line notation as a unique identifier for a specific material or material group, called the NInChI []. This led to the development of specific data reporting templates and minimal reporting standards also summarized in the first paper as well as nano-specific modification of legislation and regulatory reporting requirements like the revision of REACH technical annexes (Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/1881 []) introducing nanoforms to separate groups of nanomaterials of the same chemical core constitution but different properties.

NANoREG () was one of the earliest projects to establish minimal reporting standards based on rich metadata in the form of reporting templates (). They are based on the list of endpoints published by the OECD in 2010 for phase one of the sponsorship programme for the testing of manufactured nanomaterials () and other regulatory relevant endpoints. Technically, they are based on the ISA-TAB-Nano format () (more information is available in the first paper of this series []), are free to use and cover experimental procedures in the three areas of 1) physicochemical characterisation, 2) mammalian toxicology – *in vivo* and 3) mammalian toxicology – *in vitro*. The data resulting from the project as well as the follow-up project Nanoreg² [] are stored in the eNanoMapper data warehouse system () following a more dataset focused approach as described above as already implied by the choice of the data file format ISA-TAB, with ISA standing for Investigation, Study and Assay representing the main structure of the format. Using the linked sources approach described below, the (meta)data is now also integrated in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base in a restructured way to fit the nanomaterial-focused and data-point-focused view implemented in this database.

According to the creators, NANoREG templates can be modified to fit diverse experimental needs. Different templates in Excel format exist for specific endpoints, although different experimental methods measuring a single endpoint (e.g. nanomaterial size) are reported through a single template and, thus, cannot fully cover the specifics of the method. The NANoREG templates follow the OECD nomenclature where possible. Each template also includes the minimum set of metadata needed, according to the NANoREG project, to satisfy OECD reporting standards for the described method/protocol.

The NANoREG template structure (Figure NoR1) is divided into 4 parts. The first part, called the modules, defines the field of study (physicochemical characterisation, *in vivo* and/or *in vitro* assays) for which the template will be used. The second defines the specific Excel workbooks as per the OECD list of endpoints and includes separate sheets according to the techniques/assays used. If a user needs to add a new technique/assay they will need to add a new workbook sheet. Finally, each technique/assay is defined by the necessary experimental parameters (data and metadata). For the biological endpoints a section for

the physicochemical characterisation of the material(s) used is also included.

Figure NoR1. The NANOREG template structure

For demonstration purpose, we replicate here a part of the list for the area of mammalian toxicology – *in vivo* showing the variety of covered endpoints:

- Aerosol characterisation:
 - Mass concentration
 - Size distribution
- Bronchoalveolar Lavage:
 - Biochemical analysis inhalation
 - Cell count
 - Cellularity
- Biodistribution
- Biological effects of inhalation:
 - Histopathology
 - DNA-damage of lungs
 - Cytokine levels
 - mRNA expression *in vivo*
- ...

2.3 Address the growing diversity and complexity of nanomaterials

2.4 Instance maps to document nanomaterial fate and more

The NANoREG templates assume, besides a well-defined SOP for the endpoint resulting from the thorough validation during the production of the OECD test guidelines, that the test object can be defined by some basic information like the nanomaterial ID code e.g. from the EU JRC Nanomaterials Repository ([\(\)](#)), the CAS number and the core chemistry. The CODATA-VAMAS UDS clearly shows that even for pristine materials, such limited information is not sufficient to distinguish between or compare nanomaterials. However, it is also well known and demonstrated in the first paper of this series ([\(\)](#)) that the nanomaterial and its properties are dependent on the current environment and the different life-cycle stages the particles already went through. Therefore, additional information preferably in the form of metadata has to be provided and the data management has to be flexible enough to offer the ability to map complex experiments e.g. from nanomaterial environmental exposure and fate experiments. To encode this inseparability of the nanomaterial from its history and current environment, the NanoInformatics Knowledge Commons (NIKC) data template ([\(\)](#)), often just called “the NIKC”, was developed at the Center for the Environmental Implications of Nanomaterials (CEINT), Duke University, USA, to be used to guide curators extracting data from the scientific literature. The NIKC is an Excel-based complex template, which allows the simultaneous logging and reporting of both the experimental data and metadata (e.g. methods, instruments, images) information. It treats the experimental protocols and instruments both as data and metadata and links them automatically to the experimental data. Overall, it consists of 9 tabs to cover all the necessary bibliographic and experimental metadata, the raw/processed data and the data annotation process. Most important for this paper and a major difference to other templates, this NIKC introduces the concept of experimental instances, which translates to significant time points of the experiment, which might even cover the complete nanomaterial’s life cycle. The temporal progression can then be visualised in instance maps ([Figure NFASE1](#)) showing the transformation from one to the next instances and important information on the material at that stage and the medium / environment.

Figure NFASE1. The experimental instance, which contains the monitoring and analysis of both the material and the environment in which it exists

This possibility to describe the fate of a nanomaterial in full detail and to present it in a relatively easy way as instance maps proved beneficial for primary data collection especially for mesocosms experiments looking at nanomaterial exposure to the environment and distribution in water, soil, animals and plants at the primary and secondary exposure sites. The increasing complexity and size of such experiments profit from the dynamic and versatile templates that are able to accommodate different types and deviations of the original experiment or link back to a common starting point (e.g. nanomaterials characterisation). The NIKC offers that functionality with a tree-like structure, the trunk of which corresponds to the initial nanomaterial(s) physicochemical characterisation. Several branches then translate into various experimental variations like different exposure routes and hold the data and metadata of the various experimental instances. Examples of such trees are given in the **Results sections**. All these benefits led to the adoption and extension of the concepts and tooling around it by the NanoFASE and the NanoCommons projects. The resulting EU modified version makes input of data at the stage of data creation easier, gives more guidance on what metadata should be covered (in the NIKC case, this was determined by which metadata was available in the publications) and allows the automatic semantic annotation when inserted into the NanoCommons Knowledge Base ().

2.5 Reporting of nanoinformatics data and standard reporting templates

Besides the increasing diversity and complexity of the materials under investigation and the environment they are in, the development of new characterisation methods (wet lab and *in silico*) to replace animal testing is even more increasing the demands to data management and the metadata coverage. Since the used approaches are rarely fully standardised and validated to the degree needed to out-of-the-box acceptance by even fellow researchers not to mention risk assessors and regulators, they require a very detailed description of the models used (experimental or theoretical) and the underlying theory and prediction / simulation / measurement principle.

To enforce such detailed reporting especially for evidence generated using *in silico* approaches, ECHA has released multiple guidelines on how to use these methods in dossiers including the [“Practical guide: How to use and report \(Q\)SARs”](#) and the already mentioned [“Read-Across Assessment Framework \(RAAF\)”](#). For describing such details for quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR), as well as the training and test sets and the predictions of chemicals and materials of interest, the QSAR Model Reporting Format (QMRF) and QSAR Prediction Reporting Format (QPRF) have been defined and documents in this format are required by ECHA as part of dossiers using QSAR data. Similarly, the European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC) and the European Materials Characterisation Council (EMCC) have defined the Materials Modelling Data (MODA) and Characterisation Data (CHADA) templates to report the details of physics-based modelling approaches and physicochemical characterisation, respectively. All these formats are adopted or are currently under the process of being adopted by the nanosafety community.

The QMRF harmonised template was developed by the JRC and EU Member State authorities [Ref] and is used to summarise and report the key information of QSAR models and the result produced by respective validation studies. Being part of the dossier that accompanies a substance, its information is structured according to the OECD validation principles [Ref], and includes a defined endpoint (what is predicted), an unambiguous algorithm (a reproducible description of how predictions were produced), a defined domain of applicability (a metric of how applicable the model is to each prediction made), appropriate measures of goodness-of-fit, robustness and predictivity (overall assessment of how good the model is) and a mechanistic interpretation, if possible (an explanation of how numerical results reflect changing biological functions). The QMRF reports consists of ten sections, presented in more detail in [Ref]: 1. QSAR identifier, 2. General information, 3. Defining the endpoint - OECD Principle 1, 4. Defining the algorithm - OECD Principle 2, 5. Defining the applicability domain - OECD Principle 3, 6. Internal validation - OECD Principle 4, 7. External validation - OECD Principle 4, 8. Providing a mechanistic interpretation - OECD Principle 5, 9. Miscellaneous information, 10. Summary (JRC QSAR Model Database). A modified version of the QMRF was released by OECD in June 2021 in order to allow it to be used to report other *in silico* models (e.g. Structure Activity Relationship (SAR) models, expert systems, etc.) within skin sensitisation research and more specifically as defined in the Guideline on Defined Approaches on Skin Sensitisation (DASS) TG 497 Annex [Ref].

In parallel, the materials MODelling DAta (MODA) reporting template was developed by and is based on the Review of Materials Modelling (RoMM) [1]. It aims to provide a systematic description and documentation of simulations and models, including the user-case, solving and post-processing methods used [2]. The MODA template guides the modelers/users towards complete high-level documentation of materials models that starts with end-user cases and includes all the relevant computational details that are required for the model reproduction and curation, as well as interfacing with other models. Typical

materials models tend to be described in relation to their length scale, application, or software used. However, this description lacks information regarding the physics of the model, and is not easily interpretable by modelers that are not familiar with the terms. MODA is built on the core concepts of model entity and physics-based models that provide a common terminology with the definition of concepts and vocabulary scheme. MODA models are classified by the entity of the material (electron, atom, mesoscopic material entity, continuum volume entity), its quantities (properties of a material or phenomenon), the physics equation of the phenomenon, its material relations, its solving methods and parameters, the input pre-processing data, and the post-processing data [2].

Coupling and linking between models and their input / output are also reported in the modelling workflow of MODA. This modelling overview, along with the modelling workflow, provides users with high level data regarding the model of interest. Although MODA template was first developed for the physics-based models of materials, it can also be used for data-driven and machine learning models, such as QSAR approaches, using the same framework and structure [2]. Concepts similar to MODA have recently been developed for the description of workflows for data-centric models used in various applications [3, N1].

In a similar way, the concept of materials CHAracterization DATA (CHADA) was introduced to be applied as a building block for user studies concerning complex material characterization cases accompanied by interactions of modelling and process workflows [2, N2]. The concept of CHADA was built on the lack of a standard structure of material characterization data. The typical reported data from characterizations could vary significantly, due to differences in the sample treatment, characterization methods used, the equipment setup and calibration, and the characterization conditions [4]. Similar to MODA, CHADA provides a systematic structure consisting of user-case, data inputs regarding the sample (material type, sample treatment, dimensions, medium), the characterization method (method physics, probe, detector, equipment, calibration, setup, conditions), the data acquisition, and data post-processing) [5]. In this simplified approach, it is possible to document the experimental procedure or protocol followed during the measurements, also providing a workflow between independent, coupled or linked characterization methods and the information extracted, as in the case of MODA.

2.5 Protocol reporting questionnaires: Structured input interfaces to guide users

As shown in the previous section, the correct interpretation of an endpoint requires much more than the value itself. It is widely known that many of the physicochemical characterisation techniques for NMs impose artefacts that depend on the sample preparation steps, on the instrumental settings chosen and even on the technique chosen for measuring a specific endpoint. Techniques, e.g., for NM size, reach from very accurate but also very expensive methods like ??? to fast, cheap but less accurate methods like ???. Therefore, traditional analytical qualities such as precision, accuracy, resolution all affect correct interpretation of an NM endpoint. Many NM characterisation techniques are also oblique towards certain NM properties. Generation of the knowledge on the expectable quality and about these influences and limitations for new, innovative methods has to be based on data reported in high detail to be able to analyse all parameters influencing the results.

Since the ACEnano project [1] was developing and improving methods of very different technical readiness levels, reaching from more experimental technology to methods ready for inter-laboratory comparison testing and regulatory acceptance, being able to report all these methods and their details in

an appropriate way was seen as the highest priority of the data infrastructure. This was achieved by adopting a data reporting concept in the form of questionnaires for reporting of nanomaterial physicochemical characterisation data implemented as a web interface for the guided uploading of protocols and data. High-level standardisation was achieved by differentiating between sample preparation, measurement and data treatment protocols as the highest level and then subsections like nanomaterial information, sample description, experimental equipment and predefined sample preparation steps as the next lower level. The user is then guided through workflows to provide required fields for defining the material, the endpoint and measurement technique including the preparation steps but has then the flexibility to add method specific parameters like specific parameters of the instrument used, quality control measures and other lab-specific setting in a structured and partly semantically annotated manner. In this way, all these parameters and their optimisation throughout the development process and adaptation needed for specific materials can be analysed leading to a corpus of data for guiding future experiments regarding parameters to be chosen and finally as the basis for starting the pre-validation and validation efforts. Summing up the above, the goal of the ACEnano approach was to construct a system ensuring:

1. Flexibility of the system so that new measurement insights or new techniques can be added easily;
2. Collection of enough data and metadata to ensure current and future interpretation of NM characterisation data without the burden of collecting and storing superfluous information;
3. Creation of a database of protocols;
4. Coupling of obtained data and protocols via ontologies;
5. Reuse of metadata and data specifications of previously uploaded protocols and data to collect the community expertise on good metadata coverage practice, to encourage uptake of these practices and continuously improve them.

To address these requirements, the chosen design to implement the questionnaires was a deeply interlinked system between the protocols and the data warehouse. The questionnaires are not literally a list of questions but a number of structured and hierarchical web forms, through which the data provider is guided for filling in the metadata describing the nanomaterial, the individual experimental steps and structure of the data as well as the biographical metadata. The starting point of data upload is the specification of the protocols, both as structured metadata and also as human-readable experimental procedure with details on the individual steps. These are divided into three types: sample preparation, measurement and data treatment protocols. These protocols are stored as individual entities, which can be searched, browsed and reused in the existing or modified form. The second step is then to upload the data for a specific experiment by choosing and combining the relevant predefined protocols and supplement them with general information on the experiment and then metadata describing the nanomaterial, the specific sample and finally the data files with metadata on its format. This procedure is called data workflow in the following. Due to the variety of physicochemical characterisation methods covered by ACEnano and the existence of standard file formats for many data types, the ACEnano data warehouse stores the data just in the form provided by the user. Therefore, the solution is more a metadata than a data management system. The relationship between the protocols and data metadata is visualised in **Figure ACE1**. More information on the workflows to collect the protocol metadata and data is available in the supporting material.

Figure ACE1. The interdependencies between the two main sections of the KI (Protocols and Data)

2.6 Continuous development

Besides the improved data reporting concepts and their implementation in templates and databases described above, it is equally important to guarantee that we do not reinvent the wheel every time a new research project starts or a new database is designed. In the spirit of the first paper of this series [] demonstrating that data management needs to be performed and also designed considering all roles of the data life cycle and led by a data shepherd (or a team of), knowledge transfer has to be guaranteed to give the new projects a head-start and the possibility to reuse everything discussed before. One example, in which this was implemented is the ASINA project project [1]. It uses noticeably representative groups of nano-enabled products (NEPs) in the market (coatings and cosmetics), to formulate design hypothesis and to deliver SSbD solutions by applying a data-driven approach and methodology [Furxhi, I., et al., ASINA Project: Towards a Methodological Data-Driven Sustainable and Safe-by-Design Approach for the Development of Nanomaterials. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 2022b. 9.]. The methodology for designing new NMs/NEPs encompasses the merging of distinct data related to different scopes of the product such as improved functionality (for example anti-aging capacity for cosmetics or photocatalytic activity for textiles), cost-effectiveness, environmental sustainability and safety.

Besides the experimental and scientific challenges of monitoring and denoting the properties' alterations and the effects of NMs/NEPs during their life cycle, the biggest challenge in the data driven reasoning is the FAIR capturing of the data from synthesis, incorporation and use phase, to the end-of-life, in a transparent manner [Furxhi, I., et al., *ASINA Project: Towards a Methodological Data-Driven Sustainable and Safe-by-Design Approach for the Development of Nanomaterials. Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 2022b. 9.] [Furxhi, I., *Health and environmental safety of nanomaterials: O Data, Where Art Thou? NanoImpact*, 2022a. 25: p. 100378]. This challenge requires the active involvement and constant participation, engagement and collaboration of participants with different expertise. The ASINA paradigm provides an opportunity to illustrate and report on the trials and ongoing development of capturing, communicating, and FAIRifying complex data from multidisciplinary sources.

The data shepherd of ASINA has conceptualized and initiated the design and implementation of data FAIRification process with multiple stakeholders (i.e., data creators, data analysts and data re-users) who

are unaccustomed with the notion of data management and FAIRification process, and is currently under development [Furxhi, I., et al. (2021). *Data shepherding in nanotechnology. The Initiation. Nanomaterials* 2021a, 11(6), 1520; <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11061520>]. In ASINA, the extension of the newly defined data shepherd role is manifested with the lifecycle of the data rising from various fields, overseen and simplified, from their generation into a lab, to capturing into a worksheet and to FAIRification through the shepherd and external transnational activities. Briefly, a questionnaire is prepared and circulated among relevant stakeholders to provide a first description of the data to be generated experimentally or simulated and the protocols and standards followed. The questionnaire allows inner-communication among the partners involved in data generation and data shepherding. In addition, the protocols and standards that will be followed are reported. The questionnaire allows parties involved in a specific life cycle data generation phase and data shepherds to communicate internally and keep track of the data completeness.

[1] <https://www.asina-project.eu/>

2.7 Semantic interoperability to link sources

Finally, an optimal data management system also has to consider the data user perspective. Even if this sounds obvious, we want to stress here that data can be used in many different ways and each of them has its own preference on how the data should be presented and this is almost always quite different from how data providers want to input their data. Fortunately, modern database design building on better and better coverage of the domain by ontologies for semantic annotation allows to more and more separate data input and data provision to others. As long as data is provided based on a well defined data model, this model can be mapped on the semantic model implemented in the database and, in this way, the data can be restructured to fit the needs of the specific data user, the database is designed for. To show how this could work in the future, where project and perhaps even single experimental and computational methods would define their own data models and corresponding templates, we look at the semantic mapping approach implemented in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base (KB) to integrate (meta)data from different original resources.

The EU-project NanoCommons aims to provide an infrastructure for integrative Nanoinformatics to enable safe-by-design and integrated approaches to testing and assessment. Previous efforts in making data available and re-usable focused on ensuring that individual data-sets and measurements can be found, their context, value and constraints be understood by human data analysts. The standardisation efforts for metadata as described above aim to allow humans to comprehend the applicability of discovered data and information and how to integrate information from different assessments into combined analysis e.g. a physicochemical characterisation of a material provided by one project and its toxicological characterisation provided by another project. However, the effort of integration is left to the individual data analyst, resulting not only in redundant integration resource needs but also in differences in integration approaches and decisions.

The NanoCommons KB aims to go one step further by providing semantic interoperability to already link information from multiple sources. This interoperability has multiple levels:

1. Linking data across “same” NMs e.g. can concern different data or data sources:
 - a. Linking data type A (e.g. physicochemical characterisation) and B (e.g. Tox) and C (e.g. omics) for the “same” NM
 - b. Linking data source A (e.g. an AMBIT data warehouse), B (e.g. an RDF data set) and C (e.g. the NanoCommons data warehouse)

To enable this kind of linking additional standards need to be fulfilled by the metadata:

1. To establish “sameness” NMs need to provide either unique IDs (for example a JRC reference material ID or a registration ID at the European Registry of Materials Refs) or sufficient physicochemical characterisation information as for example specified to generate a NInChI or confirm an ECHA nanoform/read-across (Refs)
2. To link data types semantic connection between the measured parameters need to be established. For example a toxicology assay may measure the “nuclear intactness” of a certain cell line while a omics data set may measure the expression level of thousands of genes in the same cell line. In this case not only do the cell-lines need unique IDs (and the metadata of the detailed treatment protocol) but also do we need to connect gene expression (genes again needing unique IDs) to nuclear state (“nucleus” needing a unique ontology descriptor) for example by Adverse Outcome Pathways.
3. Finally, to link results from different measurements the measured parameters need to be defined by assigning ontology descriptors

The semantic model of the NanoCommons KB provides manually designed and verified mappings between the different ontologies (e.g. eNanoMapper ontology, Pathology Ontology), unique entity references (e.g. for genes Entrez IDs and ENSEMBL IDs) and database fields in the original resources. A similar approach is e.g. also used in the configurable Excel Spreadsheet Parser (NMDataParser) of the eNanoMapper Database as described in Kochev et al. [1] and in general to map different data from different projects, starting from eNanoMapper and NANoREG described above to current projects like XXX and XXX, onto the same data model. After this semantic mapping is established, data can be integrated using existing technical interfaces (application programming interfaces API) of the data sources. Similarly, the NanoCommons KB APIs could be used to access all the data either stored directly in the data warehouse or link from the other sources to be integrated into downstream analysis and modelling processes or even to be restructured to provide another view on the data. The latter could, e.g., replace the NM-centric view of the NanoCommons KB, which is designed for users interested in the characteristics of a specific material or group of materials for the safety assessment of these materials, into an endpoint-centric view, which is often preferred by *in silico* model developers, since they are in need to have large training dataset with uniform data coming from similar experimental settings. Data tools representing this latter representation are e.g. the NanoPharos database [2] and the data representation inside the Japnot modelling suite [3].

3. Results and discussion

In this section, we will present the main findings and learnings of the concepts and approaches described above targeting specific aspects of improving the metadata coverage and completeness of nanosafety research data. This is structured in the same way as the Materials and Methods section, with one subsection for each of the presented approaches.

3.1 Standardized experiments

Providing experimental evidence and the supporting data in the regulatory setting needs to follow clear rules imposed by the agencies. Therefore, projects in this area were the first confronted with the need for minimal reporting and metadata standards leading to the NANoREG template and derivatives and extensions of these. However, due to the well-defined and standardized experimental procedures including characterisation of the starting material, study design, experimental setup and processing of the resulting data, most information can directly be extracted from the corresponding OECD test guidelines, guidance documents and corresponding standard operating procedures (SOP) reducing the need for details about the experiment to be provided as metadata. For example, the general genotoxicity endpoint is described by just:

- 10 metadata fields with sample information (replicate number, NM ID code, NM chemistry (core), CAS number, vial number, NM supplier, material state, use of dispersant, dispersant reference and sample name)
- 7 fields with general information on the experiment (reporting organisation, operator, date of preparation, date of analysis, module (e.g. phys-chem, in vitro tox, in vivo tox, eco tox, ...), endpoint and assay name)
- 8 fields to characterise the size distribution (dispersion protocol, size distribution (e.g. monomodal, bimodal or multimodal), size distribution analysis method, dispersion medium, mass concentration, diameter, in weight (w) or number (n) and PDI)
- 11 experimental parameters (animal model, gender, exposure route, exposure method, exposure time, dose, animals/group, cell tissue, specific effect, method and experimental groups)
- and the reference to the SOP.

Sections of a filled-in template for this endpoint is shown in **Figure NoR2**.

Figure NoR2. Data collected in the NANoREG template for general genotoxicity

3.2 Nanomaterial characterisation at every stage

Figure NFASE2. The NIKC is a dynamic and versatile data template that allows experimental deviation, while maintaining the underlying relationships and linking back to the original nanomaterial(s)

Even if the NIKC/NanoFASE templates and the instance concept were used to collect all data produced in the NanoFASE project, only very few instance maps were actually ever created and uptake of the concept was very limited. This is unfortunate as these maps are a very helpful tool to present the design and execution of a study as demonstrated in Martinez et al. but also understandable since designing them is a very time-consuming task. Therefore, the development of a tool specialized in creating these maps was started **and a first prototype is already available.** During the discussions on what functionality this tool should offer, it became clear that instance maps could be applied also to other areas than mesocosm experiments if the strict rules, what defines a transformation from one instance to the next, and the focus on only the nanomaterial are dropped. We will demonstrate this with one example here. **Figure NFASE3** shows rules as available from the NanoFASE Data Curation Manual trying to stay as close as possible to the original NIKC specification of an instance. This results in instance maps showing mainly what happened to the nanomaterial (see examples above and as well as the instance map in Martinez et

al.) but the description of the environment is only possible in the medium nodes of an instance (see Figure NFASE1), clearly limiting the possibility to characterise biological systems before exposure and especially at different points of their development stage. Since the NanoFASE project was establishing methods to characterize the materials in complex media, the data collection using these methods but also, e.g., using complex *in vitro* systems for human hazard evaluation could profit from instances and sub-branches in the map, which are describing only the environment at different life/preparation stages and how this would lead to the final environment, which is then exposed to the nanomaterial. For an experiment investigating the concentrations of Ag nanoparticles in soil and winter wheat, this could look like as presented in Figure NFASE4. The figure was generated with the instance map tool prototype allowing also the integration of protocol nodes to better characterize the transformations from one instance to the next, which can then be linked to the protocol sections in the data template.

How do I identify my Instances?

Has a change occurred that transformed the properties of the nanomaterial or the medium?

- Functionalization of the nanomaterial
- Dispersion of the nanomaterial in solution
- Time point measurements
- Transport/Accumulation of the nanomaterial from the exposure site

Instance

Describes the chemical or biological properties of the nanomaterial and the medium at a specific moment in time.

Figure NFASE3. XXXXX

3.3 Human vs. computer readability

Examples of QMRF, MODA, CHADA

- Automatic generation of the reports from modelling software like Jaqpot
- Report can be added as part of the data

The difference to the other approaches described so far is that these templates provide the needed information to the reader thus allowing one to evaluate the usefulness of the methodology, model or measurement. QMRF, MODA and CHADA concentrate on the general background and concept of the methodology but are less specific about the materials, their current state and the complex environment it is in. Therefore, the information in the templates could be combined with information from other sources to give a holistic description of the methodology, the test system setup, the specific test material, its history and the data. Providing all this as (meta)data in one place would help other researchers and risk assessors to find and understand the data without the need to consult other documents and, in this way, highly improve interoperability with other methods/data and reusability. Especially for finding and comparing approaches to see if they are similar enough to combine data, a more machine-readable version of the formats would be very valuable.

Machine readability is a crucial part of achieving structured data findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability, according to the FAIR principles for scientific data [6]. To achieve this, MODA can be used as a base for a top-level ontology and metadata schema of material modelling, resulting in the collection of vocabularies and linkage the vocabularies barriers from different communities by harvesting common semantics from different MODA. A harmonised structure, a common terminology with ontology annotation and perhaps an even more detailed structure would further enhance the effectiveness of MODA in information exchange within materials modelling codes, a clear distinction from data-driven models and their meaning, flexibility for data sharing between multiple tools (i.e. commercial, open) and in the generation of matching codes for classes and structures.

In the same way, CHADA can increase the data interoperability based on standardization of terminology for metadata and classification with taxonomies and ontologies [4] as this has been already introduced with iCHADA as a unique means of interoperable metadata structure [9] for solid data management, data traceability and robust data quality. Semantic interoperability with ontology and taxonomy is feasible via the European Materials Modelling Ontology (EMMO) that aims towards a standard representational ontology framework based on current materials modelling and characterization knowledge [10]. Ontologies for simulations, models and optimization (OSMO [11],[12]) and software packages (VISO [12]) have been developed, which can pave the way towards the FAIRness of the data reported under the MODA/CHADA framework.

QMRF - MODA comparison:

- Do they address the same goals?
- Should they be harmonised?

- Should one replace the other?
- Should one become part of the other?
- How can we optimise human readability and machine readability at the same time and should we even try? For MODA/CHADA, I am convinced that this would be worth trying and that it might even help in achieving completeness in the reporting. I am not so sure for QMRF and it depends on what Harry/Philip answers to my questions on human-provided additional information. If this is just putting information extracted from the software into a report, then the metadata should directly be taken from the software and not the report.
- What would be the minimal information to be extracted from QMRF/MODA/CHADA usable for downstream processing (dataset search, automatic comparison of approaches, extraction of protocol/method information to be used as parameters in the modelling → to be included as independent variables in machine learning to address differences in the test data generation (zeta-potential paper from Tassos et al.).

The purpose of reporting data-based models for nanomaterials (contrasted in the MODA template to Physics-based modelling) requires detailed presentation of both the material under study and the computational methodologies employed to produce any predictions, so that any results can be reproduced, any differences across materials explained and traced back to material attributes. To this end, as outlined in Figure QMRFMODA, the MODA and QMRF reporting formats are complementary, with the MODA format including fields for detailed information on the material, its geometry and the manufacturing process. Both formats require information on the use case, software or algorithms used and the predictions produced. The QMRF report requests more detailed information on software, algorithms and predictions, detailed information on model validation and the regulatory requirements. As the MODA template also accommodates physics-based modelling, some of its fields are not relevant for data-based models: Time lapse, Equation type, name and information. At the same time, a devoted user could take advantage of the space provided by the fields in either MODA or QMRF to provide all the information required but do so in free-text format and in fields not precisely for that usage, thus sacrificing both the precision and the machine-readability of the report. It would be beneficial in future iterations of the reports to break down the information required in every field to sub-fields that would be completed using (1) a drop-down menu in the case of multiple but predefined options, (2) ontological terms from prioritised and predefined ontologies, (3) numerical values (i.e. for the fields of R2 in regression models and similarly for classification models), (4) links to the FAIRly available datasets used to generate the predictions.

Figure QMRFMODA. Diagram describing the various reporting formats and the relationships among them.

3.4 Learnings from ASINA/SABYNA?

The Excel CEINT-NIKC template with seven spreadsheet tabs, including tabs of publication, institution, people, measurement, protocol, instrument and dictionary, was selected for data and metadata capturing. The spreadsheet was selected due to its simplicity and familiarity to diverse users. The NIKC template, is modified and adapted based on the experimentation and testing strategy, where descriptors of importance are selected together with the partners to reach project goals. ASINA decided to construct case-specific templates that conceal aspects of the life cycle and capture relevant metadata to make data intelligible.

A template to insert data related to the functionality of NMs/NEPs such as the antimicrobial properties was created to fill the gap within the literature [Furxhi, I., et al. (2021c). "Data Shepherd in Nanotechnology: An Antimicrobial Functionality Data Capture Template." *Coatings* 11(12): 1486. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings11121486>] [Furxhi, I., Health and environmental safety of nanomaterials: O Data, Where Art Thou? *NanoImpact*, 2022a. 25: p. 100378]. In the latter article, the template allows flexible reporting of various functionality data such as anti-aging or anti-oxidant capacities. While safety is of primary importance within the nano-community, the performance of NMs/NEPs is also of paramount importance, since safe product that are not functional would not compete in the market. Antimicrobial data reported in a harmonized manner are scarce in the field of nano, only a few efforts exist in the literature where datasets are created manually with data extracted from the literature [Mirzaei, M., et al., A Machine Learning Tool to Predict the Antibacterial Capacity of Nanoparticles. *Nanomaterials*, 2021b. 11(7): p. 1774]. [Mirzaei, M., et al., A Supervised

Machine-Learning Prediction of Textile Antimicrobial Capacity Coated with Nanomaterials. Coatings, 2021a. 11(12): p. 1532.]

Secondly, a specific template for exposure field campaign monitoring data was developed and compared with existing ones [Furxhi, I., et al. (2021b). "Data Shepherd in Nanotechnology. The Exposure Field Campaign Template." *Nanomaterials* 11(7): 1818.]. The paper demonstrates how different stakeholders communicate their needs within the consortium and the shepherd and reveal the features of importance for specific goals within the project. For example, the raw data generated per second in the monitoring campaigns [Del Secco, B., et al., Particles Emission from an Industrial Spray Coating Process Using Nano-Materials. *Nanomaterials*, 2022. 12(3): p. 313.] might be of lower value compared to a detailed overview of all data average [Koivisto, A., et al, *Assessment of exposure determinants and exposure levels by using stationary concentration measurements and a probabilistic near-field/far-field exposure model [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]. Open Research Europe, 2021. 1(72)*]. The templates work as a comprehensive worksheet allowing users to enter data on the materials being studied, experimental settings (instrumentation and protocols), and various outcomes of interest. ges and their standard deviation produced for data-reuse purposes.

ASINA created a path for the onset of the data collection process, which is based on non-technical scientific FAIR principles that supplement the original principles and outlines the procedures involved by data creators without overcomplicating the concept [Furxhi, I., et al. (2021). *Data shepherd in nanotechnology. The Initiation. Nanomaterials 2021a, 11(6), 1520; <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11061520>*]. The ad hoc collaboration between stakeholders and the shepherd allows the generation of consensus template and is crucial to the reliability, quality and application of the data generation and capturing strategy. From a data shepherd perspective, the most challenging part was to leap from the outlined information of the questionnaire to the comprehensive state of a filled-in ready-to-use data template. A key finding is that the process is iterative until a consensus is reached between the data creators and other partners. In terms of the challenges of FAIRification, many research organizations lack the necessary expertise, and many researchers view the process as additional "administration" work that does not directly progress their work. It can be challenging for researchers who are inexperienced with the concept of data management to operationalize the principles.

Metadata capturing is not frequently promoted in regular academic practice, despite its importance. This is due to a lack of data management training and a prevalent perception of data management as something that happens after data has been thoroughly evaluated and published. Successful data management necessitates a change in the research culture, to move an organization from a protective data mentality to a mindset of data sharing and exploitation with all relevant stakeholders. To convert an organization from an inaccessible data mentality to a mindset of data sharing and exploitation with relevant stakeholders, successful data management obliges a shift in research culture. Data shepherds, because they sit at the epicenter of the data lifecycle and simplify the interaction between stakeholders, while disseminating recognition of the value of FAIR data, can accelerate this change.

The shepherd's task cannot be fulfilled without the cooperation of all partners. In some circumstances, responsible data shepherding demands perseverance and putting oneself in the unenviable position of engaging top management while micromanaging technical collaboration at the project's core. Such management is neither simple nor pleasant, and it necessitates hands-on expertise, but it is required during the cultural shift. External assistance from TA services, facilitated and sped the curation process. Until data FAIRification methods and culture are established, such projects should be fostered. Further consultations will be unnecessary after a critical mass of FAIRification implementations has been reached and training saturation has been achieved. The ASINA instances provide the scientific community with practical information about data shepherding; because this is a relatively young profession, such extensive work aids in its development.

3.5 Flexibility vs. guidance

Establishing a system of clear guidance for metadata curation is, as shown already above, essential to enforce the use of standards and improve the completeness of reported data. Templates in the form of e.g., Excel files are a first step and preferable since most data providers are familiar with their usage. However, they have clear disadvantages, some of them already described in the **Material and Method section**, be summarised and extended here:

- 1) The use of standard templates is not part of the normal experimental workflow. Instead, customised templates are often used, almost doubling the time needed for data collection (once in the customised form and once in the standard format) even if no additional metadata is requested for improving quality and completeness.
- 2) Even if spreadsheet software offers full flexibility with respect to the format, in which the data is structured, changes in the format often lead to incompatibility or even falsification of derived results.
 - a) Even if spreadsheets were originally designed for tabular data, very complex structures are nowadays implemented in them, links between different cells and equations calculating derived results based on data in specific cells. Small sometimes unintentional changes, i.e., replacing an equation by its result, can break the complete spreadsheet but are very hard to identify.
 - b) Integrating additional metadata often requires an adaptation of the automatic processing of the files, needed for the upload of the data into data warehouses. This is only possible for large amounts of data coming in this new format e.g., from a follow-up project reusing the template from its predecessor but not for individual dataset representing e.g., improvements of a specific method as done in ACEnano.
 - c) Comparing spreadsheets is very complex and, thus, it is almost impossible to, e.g., automatically translate an earlier version of a template into an updated one. This is even true for different versions of the same dataset.
 - d) One major advantage of spreadsheets is that graphs can be directly produced from the data but also that additional information like images to support the data can be integrated. However, even if it is possible to extract such graphs to include them in the data upload, identifying their purpose is impossible so that they cannot be annotated and indexed in the data warehouse.

- 3) On-the-fly validation of the collected data within the spreadsheet software requires huge development efforts. Additionally, these efforts often have to be very specific to one template or even specific methods or assays reported in these templates. However, such validation and curation is absolutely essential to produce harmonised and interoperable data, which can then be successfully indexed in data warehouses. We are here only partly talking about scientific validation, in which the data is evaluated with respect to its plausibility to identify outliers or even errors in the experiment. It is starting with the much simpler technical validation. Renaming, even if it seems minor to a human being, of column names, spelling errors and even the case insensitivity or additional white spaces can break downstream processing of the files, which can only be recovered by human curation or implementing specific correction procedures.
- 4) Even if data can be uploaded to many standard nanosafety or more general toxicology databases and data warehouses can be uploaded via web interfaces, the large majority of datasets are uploaded in the form of spreadsheets. As already expressed in point 3, validation of the files regarding the structure of the reported data has to be performed to guarantee consistency in the data warehouse. Such processing steps sometimes also require semantic annotation with ontologies and the mapping to a semantic model implemented in the data warehouse. If one of these steps fails because of errors in the files, the data uploader, which is sometimes not the same person as the data provider, needs to go back into the file to find and remove the errors often with the help of the data provider. This is a slow and time-consuming procedure.

To get beyond spreadsheets, better tools need to be developed, which allow integrating the early stages of data management directly into the normal experimental workflows. Similar to electronic lab notebooks (ELNs), which support the user to document their study designs and performed experiments in a more standardised form allowing for easy reuse, sharing but perhaps even more important already in a digitalised form to be directly integrated into reports and publications. Data management is not a strength of the existing ELNs and additional tools should be created, which give the user a natural way to collect their data directly during the experiment as electronic records. This would bring the benefits that quality controls like completeness of metadata, formal correctness and compliance to standards as well as support for ontology annotation can be directly integrated. Such tools could be even combined with ELNs to give the user one easy-to-use interface for all documentation tasks. Such tools would be clearly targeting the goal to prepare the data for upload to databases (internal) and data warehouses (public) but could be designed more independent of those and in principle just result in a spreadsheet, which the user could take as a starting point for further analysis.

The ACEnano approach is clearly not the complete solution addressing all these issues. However, it showed how modern web technology can guide the user during the collection and upload of metadata on the specific use case of the ACEnano data warehouse. The focus was on the balance between defined standards of absolutely essential metadata and flexibility to allow for adaptation of and additions to the collected metadata e.g., to cover specificities of different lab equipment. In the following, we will present some examples of how the web forms were designed to implement parts of the protocols and data workflow questionnaires.

The first example in **Figure ACE4** shows the metadata needed to describe different steps (actions) used in sample preparation. This is a relatively rigid interface and could probably also be implemented in a spreadsheet. However, the predefined actions, as well as other parameters like solvents, remove the possibility of including spelling errors and can internally be associated with the ontology entries.

Additionally, essential and optional fields can be treated separately with the first needed to be filled in before the user can progress to the next step. Additional flexibility is given by allowing the user to define customised solvents in another interface (not shown in the figure).

Part 2: Steps

Please provide details for each step (action) of your sample preparation protocol.

Step #: **Action:**

List of actions with descriptions.

Medium: + Add a new medium

Medium volume: **Volume units:** - or - **Medium weight:** **Weight units:**

Sample concentration within the medium: **Concentration units:**

Start phase: **End phase:**

Delete this step

Step #: **Action:**

List of actions with descriptions.

Speed: **Speed units:** **Speed duration:** **Duration units:**

Start phase: **End phase:**

Figure ACE4. Interface for metadata describing different actions as part of the sample preparation protocol

In the second example of **Figure ACE5** the documentation of lab equipment is presented. Here, a small number of standard fields like the name, model, software and detection limits are predefined. Specific instrument settings and parameters can then be included. At the moment, which parameters are reported is completely decided by the user but the predefined structure of the interface provides the data already in a machine-readable way and the integration of an ontology lookup service [] as shown in **Figure ACE6** harmonises the used terminology, gives semantic meaning to the metadata and reduced errors like spelling mistakes. In this way, data can be combined even if the users decide on a different ordering of the parameters. Additionally, the possibility to reuse existing protocols helps users to agree

on metadata to be reported as minimal reporting standard in an interactive process especially for methods where such do not exist yet. However, more guidance should be given in the future e.g., by providing lists of standard metadata for specific methods, assays and equipment. Finally, it should be noted that ACEnano encourages to also report on equipment often seen as less relevant like plates, pipettors, pipettes and tips but which have been shown to sometimes cause artefacts in the data. However, this cannot be enforced by the interface and has to be agreed on in best-practice guidelines.

Part 2: Equipment

Equipment

Please describe the equipment used to perform the measurement. Be sure to provide details on any instrument settings that may introduce artefacts in the final result.

Name: <input type="text"/>	Model: <input type="text"/> <small>Common instrument makes and models.</small>	Instrument type: <input type="text"/>
Software: <input type="text"/>	Software version: <input type="text"/>	
Limit of detection upper: <input type="text"/> <small>What is the largest value of the endpoint that can be measured? If there are no definite detection limits please mention the particle or medium properties that limits the detectability as a function of size.</small>	Limit of detection lower: <input type="text"/> <small>What is the lowest value of the endpoint that can be measured?</small>	Limit of detection unit: <input type="text"/>

Instrument settings and parameters (optional)
List instrument settings and parameters that might influence the measured value or its accuracy, or are of importance for reproducing the experiment. Where applicable, also give units of these settings.

<input type="text" value="Setting"/>	<input type="text" value="Value"/>	<input type="text" value="Unit"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> delete
<input type="text" value="Setting"/>	<input type="text" value="Value"/>	<input type="text" value="Unit"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> delete
<input type="text" value="Setting"/>	<input type="text" value="Value"/>	<input type="text" value="Unit"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> delete

Figure ACE5. Interface for metadata describing experimental equipment and specific instrument settings and parameters

Nanoparticles in sample

Name:

titanium dioxide nanoparticle response pathway
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/PW_0001437
A pathway triggered by exposure to titanium dioxide nanoparticle (nano-TiO₂). Nano-TiO₂ has a broad range of applications but studies indicate that under conditions of long and high dose exposure, it can exert cytotoxic and genotoxic effects. Nano-TiO₂ has been shown to induce inflammation, oxidative stress and MAP kinase activity.

titanium dioxide nanoparticles
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/XCO_0000339
Any condition in which the main

CAS number:

Crystalline phase:
Size units:
nano
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UO_0000300
A prefix in the metric system denoting a factor of 10 to the power of -9.

nanoliter
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UO_0000102
A volume unit which is equal to one thousandth of one millionth of a liter or 10^[-9] L.

nanometer
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UO_0000018
A length unit which is equal to one thousandth of one millionth of a meter or 10^[-9] m.

Figure ACE6. Ontology lookup service implemented in ACEnano to guide the data provider towards the use of harmonised and standard terminology

Figure ACE7 shows the results of reporting a measuring protocol for sample analysis by UV-Vis. The first part is the structured metadata on the endpoint, technique and equipment including the predefined fields and the user-provided specific instrument settings and parameters. The second part is a human-readable step-by-step instruction of how the experiment was performed, which is stored as metadata in addition to the structured metadata of part 1 and demonstrates one area, where the combination of ELNs and data management tools could be very beneficial by using the tooling of the ELNs to document the steps and to provide them to the protocols and data management solution to be able to store them with the data.

Sample Analysis by UV-Vis

Measurement protocol

This protocol describes quantification of the extinction of light that is measured from the spectral pattern using absorbance. UV-Vis refers to the ultraviolet to visible spectral region of light, the absorption of which is size dependent at the nanoscale. UV-Vis is therefore an ideal technique for the size characterisation of NP suspensions through absorbance at an appropriate wavelength. The settings defined below will be refined to optimise results during the subsequent runs.

Measurement

Endpoints	Average size dimension
Technique	Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis)
Type of raw data produced	- Absorption wavelength (λ) (nm) - Absorbance
Phase in which the measurement is performed	Aqueous liquid

Instruments

Instrument	UV-Vis Spectrometer		
Type of instrument	Jenway 6800		
Instrument model	Double Beam Spectrometer		
Settings and parameters	Setting	Value	Unit
	Measurement Mode	Spectrum Scan	-
	Data Mode	ABS	-
	Start Wavelength	680	nm
	End Wavelength	380	nm
	Scan Speed	400	nm/min
	Sampling Interval	0.5	-
	Slit Width	1.5	-
	Path Length	10	-
Software	Flight Deck - 1.0 & high		

Instrument	Calibrated Volume Pipettors		
Type of instrument	1 mL and 5 mL		

Instrument	Disposable tips		
Type of instrument	1 mL and 5 mL		

Steps

- 1 Switch on the spectrometer**

Switch on the UV-Vis Spectrometer and leave for 20 minutes to allow the lamp to heat up.
- 2 Prepare reference sample**

Use 18.2 MΩ-cm Ultrapure water as the reference sample
- 3 Set up the instrument parameters**

Before starting the measurements, the parameter settings should be set in the software (Flight Deck 1.0 or higher).
- 4 Baseline correction**

Baseline correction should be obtained by running a baseline using two cuvettes filled with 1 mL of Ultrapure Water each, placed in the sample holders
- 5 Add the cuvette with the sample**

The reference cuvette with 1 mL UPW should then be left untouched and the other cuvette should be replaced with a new cuvette containing 1 mL of one of the diluted AuNP suspensions. A new cuvette should be used for each different sample analysed.
- 6 Run the measurement on known samples**

Three spectrum scan runs for each known BB AuNP diluted suspension (5, 20, 40, 60 and 100 nm) should be obtained. Therefore a total of 15 scans should be collected. The results obtained should be reported as explained in data treatment protocol and a calibration curve should be plotted.
- 7 Run the measurement on unknown samples**

Following this three spectrum scan runs for the unknown monodispersed AuNP suspension containing a mono-dispersed suspension of NPs of an unknown size.

Protocol development phase: Cross lab testing (VPE)
 Confidentiality: Restricted Access only to ACEnano project members
 Organisation: UoB - The University of Birmingham
 Project: ACEnano - Analytical and Characterisation Excellence in nanomaterial risk assessment: A tiered approach
 Protocol version: 1
 Protocol status: a
 Original protocol name: Ultraviolet-visible Light Spectroscopy (UV-Vis)
 ACEnano ID: Ultraviolet-visible Light Spectroscopy (UV-Vis)

Figure ACE7. Metadata provided for a measurement protocol analysing a NM sample with UV-Vis

An important part of the data workflow is to provide information on the sample (see Figure ACE8), which will be used here as the last example of the ACEnano metadata capturing approach and relate it to the NanoFASE approach described above. The sample is described in detail using different parameters (names and other identifiers, the sample physicochemical characteristics like its phase, vehicle, volume, weight, concentration, etc). The nanomaterials that are contained in the sample are also described separately using different identifiers and physicochemical parameters. In addition, information regarding the storage conditions as well as a representative image of the sample can be added to the workflow. At the moment, this webform is quite rigid with the only flexible part consisting of the possibility to specify multiple nanoparticles to allow for covering of mixtures. However, as presented in the description of the NanoFASE concept, the NM might have already undergone multiple transformation due to environmental or human exposure and this fate and lifecycle state has an immense influence on the NM characteristics and needs to be reported with the data. Therefore, the concept of instances needs to be included in the ACEnano metadata schema in the near future to go beyond the requirements of the ACEnano project and allowing the linking of physicochemical characterisation data with exposure, fate and finally hazard data stored in other databases for samples of the same lifecycle state of a NM. Additionally, new specifications to unambiguously identify an NM down to a specific nanoform or to group experiments based on the same starting material should be included based on the InChI for nano line notification [] and the European Registry for Materials [], respectively.

Sample

Name:

Code: Supplier: Batch number:

Sample phase:

Medium: +Add a new medium

Sample volume: Volume units:

Sample weight: Weight units:

Concentration of material in sample: Concentration units:

Nanoparticles in sample

Core chemistry: Standard identifier: CAS number:

If available, please add the standard identifier of the nanomaterial, for example the [JRC Code for Representative Nanomaterials](#) or similar.

Coating: Crystalline phase: Shape:

Size: Size units:

Surface area: Surface area units:

Coating thickness: Units:

Delete this nanoparticle

+ Add nanoparticle

Arrival and storage

Date of arrival: Packaging:

Storage temperature: Temperature units: Storage at dark conditions:

Sample image

Image: | No file chosen

Figure ACE8. Metadata used for the description of the sample analysed

3.7 Integration vs. catalog

Establishing a way to archive and make publicly available data generated with significant effort of time and resource should be the absolute minimum requirement for any publicly funded data generation

effort, whether it is a research project or a regulatory process. However, as signified by the FAIR data movement (Ref) and the previous sections, archiving and open access are necessary but not sufficient pre-conditions for re-use. In addition we need sufficient metadata to become aware of and make sense of the available data. Still, even FAIR data requires major effort before it can be used in an integrative analysis such as Safe-by-design and IATA require. Consequently, in integrative data analysis almost 80% of research time is spent on data discovery and pre-processing rather than the actual analysis task (Ref). To lessen this pain and in addition provide a more replicable, integrated data source the NC KB provides mechanisms to integrate heterogeneous information both across data types and across data sources.

To this end we developed a semantic model that connects the different concepts involved in Safe-by-design or IATA such as “NanoMaterial”, “Instance” or measured “Parameter” as shown in Figure X. Whenever available the concepts in the semantic model are mapped to unique entity references such as Gene IDs from Entrez or ontology terms. The modelling of concepts as nodes such as “NanoMaterial” or edges like “is part of” allow rich semantic mappings such as “NanoMaterial is part of Instance”.

Figure X: Semantic Model of the NC KB. Concepts are displayed as nodes such as “NanoMaterial” or edges like “is part of”. Colouring is used solely to exemplify some semantic relatedness such as “Compound” and NanoMaterial” or “Gene” and “Protein”.

Based on this semantic model the NC KB provides manually developed mappings for different data types and sources. For data managed directly within the data warehouse of the NC KB this results in physicochemical, toxicological, omics and computational data from different data sources being mapped to the same NM. As of now “same NM” in this case really means NM identified by the same ID while Instance specific information such as aging procedures are not necessarily mapped and therefore associated data sits in parallel Instances connected to the same NM. Currently these encompass 567

NMs with associated data from 4136 physicochemical characterisations, 4898 toxicity assays, 204 omics data sets and 170 computational predictions.

In addition to its data warehouse function, the NC KB provides a data catalogue to make data hosted by the various data management systems developed in different research projects easier to find. While theoretically a fully “FAIR” data warehouse would allow us to automatically find and interoperate data from different sources and data types we are still far from reaching this state as exemplified by a recent FAIRness assessment (Ref Ammar et al). In addition, we currently lack tools that translate available computational re-useability into user interfaces for less computationally inclined persons. Therefore we have manually mapped APIs from data warehouse software such as AMBIT (Ref Jeliaskova et al.) or SPARQL based datasets to the NC KB semantic model, enabling a graphical user interface (as well as an API) to search and explore across multiple NMs and datasets. Currently, AMBIT based data warehouses for NanoReg, NanoReg2 and eNanoMapper data are available in the NC KB data catalogue, providing information on 902 NMs and 73 measured parameters (“endpoints”). Once users have identified data of interest they can directly access the linked data entry in the corresponding AMBIT data warehouse to access the measurement results.

To showcase the advantage of semantically mapped data types we have implemented a graphical “data completeness” assessment. Based on reviews by GRACIOUS, the ToxRTool and NInChI developers and ECHA read-across guidelines (Ref) we specified a set of relevant use cases and required information for these (see Table X).

Table X: Use case – required information mapping

Information group	Required Information	Use case				
		Grouping/Read-across (ECHA recommendation)	Nanoform identification (REACH requirement)	QSAR e.g. Tox prediction	Regulatory requirement (REACH/OECD)	NInChI calculation
Basic	Core Compound	+	+	+	+	+
	Compound(s) of Coating/Doping/Functionalisation	+	+	+	+	
	Purity of tested NM	+		+		

	Concentration/Dose			+		
	Doping rate			+		
	pH			+		
PhysChem						
	Crystallinity	+	+			+
	Surface area	+	+			
	Dustiness	+				
	Water solubility	+		+		
	Surface hydrophobicity	+		+		
	Surface charge	+		+		
	Shape	+	+	+		+
	Size	+	+	+	+	+
	Zeta potential	+		+	+	
	Chirality					+
	Dispersibility	+				
Tox						
	Test model (organism/strain, cell line, in-vitro assay)	+		+		
	design (frequency + duration of exposure, time-points)	+		+		

	observation, controls)					
	no. of replications	+		+		
	Endpoint description (what, how determined)			+		
	Biological reactivity (ROS production)	+				
	Photoreactivity (ROS production)	+				
	data analysis method	+		+		
	SOP/Protocol/guidelines followed	+		+		
Computational						
	Software (what, version)					
	Parameter settings					

Based on these use-case – information mappings we developed a completeness test that queries for a given use-case and NM the required list of measured parameters and metadata needed to be able to execute this use case. The completeness check therefore occurs on the level of available information for a specific NM rather than the legacy level of individual datasets. In this way completeness is defined by the full set of available information independent of the history of

different datasets providing parts of information. The result of such a completeness check can be reported graphically as well as numerically (Figure X).

Nanomaterial	Grouping/read-across	Nanoform identification	-	NInChI	-	QSAR model development	-	Regulatory	-	Tox-prediction PhysChem
NP00193	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		38% [3/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]
NP00194	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		50% [4/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]
NP00195	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		50% [4/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]
NP00196	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		50% [4/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]
NP00197	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		50% [4/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]
NP00198	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00214	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		50% [4/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]
NP00221	13% [1/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		25% [2/8]		0% [0/2]		17% [1/6]
NP00222	13% [1/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		25% [2/8]		0% [0/2]		17% [1/6]
NP00223	13% [1/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		25% [2/8]		0% [0/2]		17% [1/6]
NP00224	13% [1/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		25% [2/8]		0% [0/2]		17% [1/6]
NP00225	13% [1/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		25% [2/8]		0% [0/2]		17% [1/6]
NP00226	13% [1/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		25% [2/8]		0% [0/2]		17% [1/6]
NP00234	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00235	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00236	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00241	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00242	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00243	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00244	0% [0/8]	0% [0/4]		17% [1/6]		13% [1/8]		0% [0/2]		0% [0/6]
NP00254	25% [2/8]	25% [1/4]		33% [2/6]		38% [3/8]		50% [1/2]		33% [2/6]

Figure X: Graphical representation of data completeness. Here individual columns represent different use cases from "grouping/read-across" to "nanoform identification", "NInChI generation", "QSAR model development" and "Regulatory application" to "Toxicology prediction model".

4. Conclusion

The above approaches are mainly based on predefined templates in the form of spreadsheets or text documents, as in the case of the MODA templates [ref]. However, there are some technical issues associated with such approaches:

1. They are useful to define the metadata coverage within a project, especially if the study designs have already been prepared or even where the data has already been collected. However, if the templates are then used in other projects or by organisations outside the consortia, the templates may be suboptimal, since fields might be ambiguously defined even if their meaning was clear to the original project or new fields would be needed in order to follow the scientific progress. Also, the fixed structure prohibits reporting of important new metadata or the existing fields are misused.
2. Even if metadata templates are now more often shared between projects guaranteeing some sort of harmonisation, additions and improvements are often needed and introduced (see point 1). Such improvements are hard to spot in spreadsheets or free-text templates rendering it impossible for new users to select the best template. Additionally, these improvements are done in parallel in different projects but are not exchanged by these projects and thus, are not combined to generate even more complete templates.
3. Automatic user guidance and quality control can be integrated in such templates only in a very restricted way. Consistency of a spreadsheet can be completely destroyed by changing the format slightly, removing links between cells or equations and providing information where it doesn't belong or omitting important information.

To address these issues, a more controlled but still flexible approach is needed. This should, on the one hand, allow continuous improvement of the templates but, on the other hand, profit and preserve the experience and know-how of the nanosafety community with respect to the most significant metadata, especially with respect to reuse of the data.

References

Supplement materials

ACEnano protocol and data workflows

2.5.1 Protocols

Three types of protocols are supported:

- **Sample preparation:** Outline of steps that were taken to prepare the original sample for measurement;
- **Measurement protocol:** The prepared sample is measured by a technique to yield a value for an endpoint. The measurement is described by technique-specific parameters that are crucial for the reproducibility and accuracy of endpoint values;

- **Data treatment:** Description of steps taken to extract the measurement results from raw data.

The protocol forms contain predefined or free text fields, as well as compulsory or optional sections. In this way, the user has enough flexibility in what to add to the protocol, but at the same time assure that the essential elements are captured. The main sections are listed below in **Figure ACE2**. In addition, selected fields are annotated with an ontology term supporting the goal of harmonisation and integration with other databases. All protocols are compiled in the ACEnano repository and are further used to create the data workflows (see next section). Once a protocol is submitted, it cannot be modified (except the confidentiality and license information). This feature was implemented to prevent protocols from being changed and potentially falsifying data workflow and datasets they are used in. However, the users can create copies of any of the submitted protocols, modify and save them as a new version or variant of that particular protocol to avoid reentering of metadata common in only slightly modified and optimised protocols e.g., resulting from new developments of a method or adopting it to another type of NM.

Sample preparation protocol	
Part 1: General information	Protocol name and description
	Contacts
	Technique and Endpoints
Part 2: Steps	Multiple actions and action parameters
→ Preview protocol, Make more changes & Submit protocol	

Measurement protocol	
Part 1: General information	Protocol name and description
	Contacts
	Technique and Endpoints
Part 2: Equipment	Instrument settings
	Type of datasets produced
	Measurement quality parameters
Part 3: Steps	Protocol steps
→ Preview protocol, Make more changes & Submit protocol	

Data treatment protocol	
Part 1: General information	Protocol name and description
	Contacts
	Technique and Endpoints
Part 2: Steps	Steps and algorithm used
→ Preview protocol, Make more changes & Submit protocol	

Figure ACE2. Main components of the protocol questionnaires

2.5.2 Data

The 'data' in this context refers to metadata and data files provided in the data workflows and file upload. In order to create a workflow, the user combines existing protocols and adds sample information and nanomaterial identification and description. To differentiate the workflows depending on their purpose, they can be labelled as 'Analysis, Calibration or Blank' workflows that correspond to the type of experimental runnings performed usually in a study. The concept of studies was mainly introduced for the inter-laboratory comparison studies (round robins) performed in ACEnano but they can be used in general to group data sets performed in a specific experiment. At the end of the process the data files are uploaded. The form to create such a workflow is divided into seven steps (see **Figure ACE3**):

1. Technique and endpoints - selection of the technique used in the analysis and which endpoints were measured;
2. Sample protocol - selection of the sample preparation protocol that was used (if applicable);
3. Measurement protocol - selection of the measurement protocol;
4. Data treatment protocol - selection of the data treatment protocol that was used (if applicable);
5. General information - analysis name, type, description and contact information;
6. Sample description - description of the sample and identification of the nanomaterial analysed;
7. Data upload - uploading of raw, processed and summary data files.

1 Technique and endpoints — 2 Sample protocol — 3 Measurement protocol — 4 Data treatment protocol

5 General information — 6 Sample description — 7 Data upload — 8 Preview

Technique and Endpoints

In the lists below mark techniques and endpoints for which this analysis was done.
(List of endpoints and techniques covered by the ACEnano project).

Technique:*

----- ▾

Endpoints:*

Figure ACE3. Entry point for the creation of a data workflow and upload of data files

Example MODA file

A MODA template was produced to describe the calculation of nanodescriptors has been published recently by NanoCommons members. In this template full details of the simulation approach are provided in the Modelling Data (MODA) format.

MODA for *calculation of full-particle structural and energetic NANODESCRIPTORS*

Simulated in the NanoSolveIT project

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION		
1	USER CASE	<i>Structural and energetic nano-descriptors of spherical nanoparticles</i>
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1 <i>Material (atomistic) using molecular dynamics (LAMMPS)</i>
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	<i>K. Tämm, L. Sikk, J. Burk, R. Rallo, S. Pokhrel, L. Mädler, J. J. Scott-Fordsmand, P. Burk, T. Tamm, Parametrization of nanoparticles: development of full-particle nanodescriptors, Nanoscale, 36, 2016, 16243-16250</i> <i>J. Burk, L. Sikk, P. Burk, B. B. Manshian, S. J. Soenen, J. J. Scott-Fordsmand, T. Tamm, K. Tämm, Fe-Doped ZnO nanoparticle toxicity: assessment by a new generation of nanodescriptors, Nanoscale, 46, 2018, 21985-21993</i>
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	<i>The software is released under the GNU General Public License (GPL). LAMMPS - Plimpton, P. "Fast Parallel Algorithms for Short-Range Molecular Dynamics", Journal of Computational Physics Volume 117, Issue 1, 1 March 1995, Pages 1-19.</i> https://lammps.sandia.gov/ (3 Mar 2020 release)
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	<i>The calculation requires the structure (i.e. coordinates of all atoms) of a nanoparticle and input parameters (Buckingham and Coulomb force field parametrization) to calculate structural and energetic descriptors of the nanoparticle</i>

Workflow picture

Figure S2: The workflow picture for the full-particle structural and energetic nanodescriptor simulation. At present this model is stand-alone, but in due course all descriptors will be precalculated and integrated into the NanoSolveIT integrated approach to testing and assessment (IATA) at which time the workflow will be extended as these descriptors will serve as inputs to subsequent models.

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<i>Full-particle nano-descriptors calculated using molecular mechanics to evaluate the toxicity of Me_xO_y nanoparticles.</i>
1.2	MATERIAL	<i>Any material that has the chemical formula Me_xO_y (Me_xO_y, where x and y are integers)</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<i>Spherical system ranging from nanometre to micrometre</i>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>Not applicable</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<i>Not relevant</i>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	<i>K. Tämm, L. Sikk, J. Burk, R. Rallo, S. Pokhrel, L. Mädler, J. J. Scott-Fordsmand, P. Burk, T. Tamm, Parametrization of nanoparticles: development of full-particle nanodescriptors, <i>Nanoscale</i>, 36, 2016, 16243-16250. 10.1039/C6NR04376C</i>

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	<i>Newton's equation-based models – molecular mechanics based on empirical force fields</i>	
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	<i>Atoms</i>	
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS / CHEMISTRY EQUATION (PE)	Equation	<i>Newton's equations of motion</i>
		Physical quantities	<i>Coordinates and mass of each atom, interatomic potentials</i>
2.3	MATERIALS RELATIONS (MR)	Relation	<i>Buckingham and Coulomb potential functions</i>
		Physical quantities / descriptors for each MR	<p><i>The Coulomb potential includes the partial charge of each atom and the dielectric constant of the medium in which the material is dispersed</i></p> <p><i>The Buckingham potential includes atom pair parameters (combination of two elements) and generic parameters such as the cut-off distance</i></p>

2.4	SIMULATED INPUT	<i>Not applicable at present. Will be updated once the model is integrated into the NanoSolveIT IATA.</i>
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3	SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS	
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	<i>Energy minimization schemes (e.g. Polak-Ribiere version of the conjugate gradient algorithm) using Particle-Particle Particle-Mesh (PPPM) summation for long-range Coulomb potentials.</i>

3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	<i>LAMMPS, http://lammps.sandia.gov</i>	
3.3	TIME STEP	<i>Not applicable</i>	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	<p><i>The Buckingham and Coulomb potentials are hardcoded as function of atoms type and position.</i></p> <p><i>Atoms are represented as material points.</i></p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<i>periodic boundary conditions expressing infinite domain</i>	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · <i>stopping tolerance for energy (10^{-4} unitless)</i> · <i>stopping tolerance for force (10^{-6} in eV/Angstrom)</i> · <i>max iterations of minimizer (100)</i> · <i>max number of force/energy evaluations (100000)</i> · <i>relative error in forces for the PPPM summation (10^{-5} unitless)</i> 	

4

POST PROCESSING

4.1

THE PROCESSED OUTPUT

The following descriptors are computed:

- Total number of atoms in the NP
- Total number of atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Total number of atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, number of atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, number of atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical, species, number of atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average per-atom potential energy for all atoms in the NP
- Average per-atom potential energy for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average per-atom potential energy for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average per-atom potential energy for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average per-atom potential energy for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average per-atom potential energy for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average HEX real part for all atoms in the NP
- Average HEX real part for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average HEX real part for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX real part for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX real part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX real part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average HEX imaginary part for all atoms in the NP
- Average HEX imaginary part for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average HEX imaginary part for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX imaginary part for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX imaginary part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX imaginary part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average CN for all atoms in the NP
- Average CN for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average CN for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average CN for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average CN for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average CN for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average PTM parameter for all atoms in the NP
- Average PTM parameter for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average PTM parameter for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average PTM parameter for all atoms of a particular species in the NP

- *For each chemical species, average PTM parameter for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average PTM parameter for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP*
- *Average per-atom force vector length for all atoms in the NP*
- *Average per-atom force vector length for all atoms residing in the core of the NP*
- *Average per-atom force vector length for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average per-atom force vector length for all atoms of a particular species in the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average per-atom force vector length for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average per-atom force vector length of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP*
- *Average normal component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms in the NP*
- *Average normal component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the core of the NP*
- *Average normal component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average normal component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species in the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average normal component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the core of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average normal component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP*
- *Average tangential component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms in the NP*
- *Average tangential component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the core of the NP*
- *Average tangential component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average tangential component of the force vector of a particular species in the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average tangential component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the core of the NP*
- *For each chemical species, average tangential component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP*
- *NP diameter*
- *NP surface area*
- *NP volume*
- *NP lattice energy*
- *NP lattice energy per unit diameter*
- *NP lattice energy per unit surface area*
- *NP lattice energy per unit volume*
- *Relative NP lattice energy to the lattice energy of the bulk material*

where HEX is hexagonal order parameter, CN is coordination number and PTM is polyhedral template matching.

METHODOLOGIES

The per-atom potential energy is computed by summing all energetic contributions (pair, bond, angle, etc.) that the atom is part of. Each energy contribution is produced by a small set of atoms (e.g. 2 atoms in a bond or pair-wise interaction, 4 atoms in a dihedral or 3 atoms in a Tersoff 3-body interaction) and the energy is assigned in equal proportions to each atom in the set. E.g. 1/4 of the dihedral energy assigned to each of the 4 atoms and 1/2 of the bond energy assigned to each of the two atoms.

The hexagonal order parameter, η , of the i^{th} atom is a complex number defined as

where the sum is over the $N = 6$ nearest neighbors of the central i^{th} atom. The angle θ is formed by the vector \mathbf{r}_{ij} and the x axis. η is calculated only using the x and y components, whereas the distance from the central atom is calculated using all three (x, y, and z) components of the bond vector. The complex number η is restricted to the unit disk of the complex plane i.e.

The coordination number of an atom counts the number of neighbor atoms (irrespective of atom type) that lie within a specified distance from the given atom. The distance is related to the ionic radii of the atoms in the NP; it is equal to 1.2 times the maximum ionic radius of the species present in the NP.

The PTM parameter of atom i is the square-root mean square deviation (RMSD) between its actual position and its position in one of seven perfect lattices. The seven types of lattices are face-centered cubic, hexagonal close-packed, body-centered cubic, icosahedral, simple cubic, diamond cubic, diamond hexagonal, graphene. The identification of the ideal lattice is done employing the polyhedral template matching method.

The per-atom force vector length is computed as $|\mathbf{F}_i|$ where \mathbf{F}_i is the per-atom force vector and x, y, z are the three cartesian axes.

The tangential component of the per-atom force vector is computed as F_{tan} where \mathbf{r}_i and \mathbf{r}_{cm} are position vectors of the i^{th} atom and the center of mass of the NP. The normal component is computed as the difference between the per-atom force vector and the tangential component.

The NP diameter, D , is computed as twice the maximum distance of an atom from the center of mass of the NP. The NP surface area and volume are calculated as A and V .

The NP lattice energy is the product of the average per-atom potential energy and the number of atoms in the unit cell. The NP lattice energy relative to the lattice energy of

		<p><i>the bulk material is the difference between the average per-atom potential energy of the bulk material and the average per-atom potential energy of the NP multiplied by the number of atoms in the unit cell structure.</i></p> <p><i>The parameters described in the sections above are spatially averaged in three ways:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>(i) Arithmetic average over all atoms belonging to the NP</i> <i>(ii) Arithmetic average over all atoms with a distance less than a given radius specified by the user from the center-of-mass of the NP. This region corresponds to the “core” region of the NP</i> <i>(iii) Arithmetic average over all atoms which belong to the NP but not to the “core”</i> <p><i>There is also averaging with respect to the chemical nature of the various species:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>(i) Arithmetic average over all atoms of the same chemical species</i> <i>(ii) Arithmetic average over all atoms irrespective of their chemical species.</i>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	<i>Not applicable</i>

In the same study, Cytotoxicity of metal oxide (Me_xO_y) nanoparticles on BEAS-2B and RAW 264.7 cells, in order to demonstrate how the developed models are harmonized with the OECD principles for (Q)SAR model validation for regulatory purposes (OECD, 2004), all the available information about the development and evaluation of the read-across model was included in a QMRF report. For this purpose, the guidance of the JRC QSAR Model Database is followed, making the necessary alterations for nanoinformatics data (Joint Research Centre, 2017).

Principle 1 – A defined endpoint.

Species	Combined human bronchial epithelial (BEAS-2B) and murine myeloid (RAW 264.7) cell lines
Endpoint	Cytotoxic effects of metal oxide (Me_xO_y) nanoparticles (NPs) – 24-hour toxicity to BEAS-2B and RAW 264.7 (measured as cell viability)
Endpoint comments	% cell viability
Endpoint units	% cell viability
Dependent variable	For each effective concentration, the cytotoxicity (% remaining living cells) of Me_xO_y s NPs was calculated.

Experimental protocol	<p>Full experimental description can be found in Zhang et al., ACS Nano. 2012 May 22; 6(5): 4349–4368. doi:10.1021/nn3010087</p> <p>Short description: Cell viability was determined by LDH and ATP assays, which were carried out with CytoTox 96® (Promega Corporation, Madison, WI), CellTiter 96® AQueous (Promega Corporation) and ATPlite™ 1step (Perkin Elmer, Boston, MA) assay kits, respectively. Ten thousand cells in 100 µL medium (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) for the RAW cells and bronchial epithelial growth medium (BEGM) for the BAES-2B cells) were plated in each well of a 96 multi-well black plate (Costar, Corning, NY) for overnight growth. The medium was removed and cells treated for 24 hr with 100 µL of a series of Me_xO_y NP suspensions to yield final concentrations of 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2, 6.3, 12.5, 25, 50, 100 and 200 µg/mL</p> <p>24 NP stock solutions (5 mg/mL) were prepared by dispersing the dry particles in deionized water through probe sonication (3 W). The stock solution was used to remove 40 µL aliquots which were mixed with an equal volume of 4% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Fraction-V, Gemini Bioproducts, USA) and equilibrated for 1 h at room temperature. Cell culture medium (920 µL DMEM) was added to the BSA-coated NP suspensions. The NP suspensions were sonicated (3 W) for 15 seconds prior to conducting cellular studies. For the BEAS-2B exposures, 2 mg/mL of BSA was added to the BEGM for preparation of the series of NP suspensions at different concentrations.</p>
Endpoint data quality and variability	Different NP concentrations were assessed (range 0 – 200 µg/mL)

Principle 2 – An unambiguous algorithm.

Type of model	Machine learning, <i>k</i> -nearest neighbour (<i>k</i> NN) algorithm
Explicit algorithm	Use <i>k</i> NN with <i>k</i> value equal to 3.
Descriptors in the model	Statistically significant descriptors used for prediction: NP core size, NP hydrodynamic size, assay type, exposure dose, energy of the conduction band (E_c), the coordination number of metal atoms in the NP (Coord. #Me atoms) and the force vector surface normal component of atoms ($V \perp \#all\ atoms$).
Descriptor selection	<p>Number and type of descriptors initially screened: 77 descriptors. For full list see Table S1.</p> <p>Method used to select the descriptors: <i>BestFirst</i> variable selection along with <i>CfsSubsetEval</i> evaluator.</p>

Algorithm and descriptor generation	Experimental measurements (see Zhang et al. (2012) for full details). In summary the measured parameters were % BEAS-2B and RAW 264.7 cell viability (survival) as a function of applied Me_xO_y NP dose at 24 hours. The kNN algorithm was used for model generation.
Software name and version for descriptor generation	LAMMPS (https://lammmps.sandia.gov/) See ESI Appendix 1 for attached MODA template for atomistic descriptors
NPs/Descriptors ratio	49.29 (345:7, number of data rows divided by the number of significant descriptors in the training set)

Principle 3 – A defined domain of applicability.

Description of the applicability domain of the model	The applicability domain (AD) is defined by fixed boundaries (threshold). The threshold is calculated by considering Euclidean distances between all training set NPs.
Method used to assess the applicability domain	Euclidean distance method among all training and test NPs. The distance of each test NP or each external NP to each nearest neighbour of the training NPs set is compared to a predefined AD threshold; if this distance is lower than the threshold then its endpoint prediction can be considered reliable.
Software name and version for applicability domain assessment	Enalos+ nodes version 1.0 (see Afantitis et al. (2020), DOI : 10.2174/0929867327666200727114410)
Limits of applicability	APD threshold: 2.645. Calculated using the average and standard deviation of all Euclidian distances in the training set. Predictions outside this threshold are considered unreliable.

Principle 4 – Appropriate measures of goodness-of-fit, robustness and predictivity.

Availability of the training set	<p>Data available via NanoPharos at https://db.nanopharos.eu/</p> <p>Dataset name: Papadimitris et al. (2020), Predicting cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles using Isalos Analytics platform</p> <p>Information: Dataset retrieved from S2Nano database (data produced by Zhang et al. (2012, doi:10.1021/nn3010087).</p> <p>Atomistic descriptors produced as per Tamm et al. (2016), doi:10.1039/C6NR04376C.</p>
Available information for the training set	<p>24 tested Me_xO_y NPs: Al₂O₃, CuO, CeO₂, Co₃O₄, CoO, Cr₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄, Gd₂O₃, HfO₂, In₂O₃, La₂O₃, Mn₂O₃, NiO, Ni₂O₃, Sb₂O₃, SiO₂, SnO₂, TiO₂, WO₃, Y₂O₃, Yb₂O₃, ZnO, ZrO₂</p> <p>Analytical information on the experimental process can be found in Zhang et al., ACS Nano. 2012 May 22; 6(5): 4349–4368. doi:10.1021/nn3010087</p>
Data for each descriptor variable for the training set	Yes
Data for the dependent variable (response) for the training set	Yes
Other information about the training set	Total of 345 data points for the dependent variable (% cell availability) from 24 NPs: 37 toxic, 308 non-toxic.
Pre-processing of data before modelling	Gaussian normalization of descriptors
Statistics for goodness-of-fit	Tropsha's tests, i.e. the coefficient of determination between experimental values and model predictions (R ²), validation through an external test set, leave-many-out cross validation procedure and Quality of Fit and Predictive Ability of a continuous QSAR Model, as per Tropsha, A., Best Practices for QSAR Model Development, Validation, and Exploitation. Molecular Informatics 2010, 29, (6-7), 476-488 https://doi.org/10.1002/minf.201000061
R ² > 0.6	0.91
R _{c_{ext}} > 0.5; Result: 0.904	0.904
(R ² -R ₀ ²)/R ² < 0.1	0.022
(R ² -R ₀ ¹²)/R ² < 0.1	0.002
R ² -R ₀ ¹² < 0.3	0.018

0.85 < k < 1.15	0.994
0.85 < k' < 1.15	1.005
Robustness – Statistics obtained by Y-scrambling	Accuracy in test = 0.406-0.694 (10 iterations)
Robustness – Statistics obtained by bootstrap	Yes, see above
Robustness – Statistics obtained by other methods	Yes, see above
Availability of the external validation set	Yes
Available information for the external validation set	Yes
Data for each descriptor variable for the external validation set	Yes
Data for the dependent variable for the external validation set	Yes
Other information about the external validation set	Total 149 data points from 24 Me _x O _y NPs. 14 toxic and 135 non-toxic NPs
Experimental design of test set	Partition of the initial dataset using random, stratified sampling (70:30 training : test sets)
Predictivity – Statistics obtained by external validation	R ² > 0.6; Result: 0.91 R _{cvext} > 0.5; Result: 0.904 (R ² -R ₀ ²)/R ² < 0.1; Result: 0.022 (R ² -R ₀ ¹²)/R ² < 0.1; Result: 0.002 R ² -R ₀ ¹² < 0.3; Result: 0.018 0.85 < k < 1.15; Result: 0.994 0.85 < k' < 1.15; Result: 1.005
Predictivity – Assessment of the external validation set	The external validation set is the 30% of the initial dataset and all predictions for the validation set fall within the domain of applicability

Comments on the external validation of the model	N/A
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Principle 5 – A mechanistic interpretation.

Mechanistic basis of the model	<p>Exposure dose, NP size and surface characteristics related to the specific metal constituting the NP play a significant role in toxicity of Me_xO_y NPs to BEAS-2B and RAW 264.7 cell toxicities.</p> <p>The cells have different functionalities (epithelial barrier versus phagocytotic, respectively) and as such are expected to internalise NPs to different extents.</p> <p>Care must be taken when predicting results, as the assay type used for experimental data production plays a significant role.</p>
A priori or a posteriori mechanistic interpretation	<p>Me_xO_y NP toxicity can be predicted using a combination of physicochemical, assay-related and atomistic descriptors. Higher doses of NPs lead to higher toxicity. Furthermore, the stability of the NP surface plays a significant role, as the higher the force vector of surface metal atoms the higher the potential for ion leaching and NP dissociation that can lead to toxicity from the release metal cations.</p>
Other information about the mechanistic interpretation	No other information available.

MODA in a **spreadsheet** format designed for accounting the MODA features in a simple unified approach persisting the same concepts of the original MODA templates (aspect of system, model equation, modeling metadata, post-processing), but with an increased information about the modeling methodology and modeling tool per sheet/concept. The MODA shown here was produced first in the original MODA format and transferred viz. modified to the spreadsheet format. This particular example serves to describe the calculation of potential of mean forces of amino acids on a nanoparticle surface by metadynamics simulations:

Workflow:

Spreadsheet MODA template:

1. Aspect of System (material)

	Area	Subarea	Standard metadata	Example	Unit	Version	Literature
1.1	Aspect of User Case			Atomistic model of the material surface			
1.2	Material			material surface (any)			
1.3	Geometry			a surface slab of the material, presented in terms of atomic cartesian coordinates and bonds between the atoms, periodic in two dimensions (XY plane)			

1.4	Time Lapse			n.a.			
1.5	Manufacturing process			user input prepared by an external software			
1.6	Publication						

1. Aspect of System (sorbent)

	Area	Subarea	Standard metadata	Example	Unit	Version	Literature
1.1	Aspect of User Case			Atomistic model of sorbent molecule			
1.2	Material			biomolecule			
1.3	Geometry			isolated molecule			
1.4	Time Lapse			n.a.			
1.5	Manufacturing process			Prepared set of biomolecules described by the molecular topology files			
1.6	Publication						

1. Aspect of System (overall system)

	Area	Subarea	Standard metadata	Example	Unit	Version	Literature
1.1	Aspect of User Case			Simulation box with material surface, sorbent and solvent			
1.2	Material			material surface (any), sorbent (Nanobiomol)			

				dataset), water			
1.3	Geometry			rectangular box with 3D boundary conditions			
1.4	Time Lapse			thermodynamic limit			
1.5	Manufacturing process			Solvent molecules are added in the simulation box. Material slab periodic in X and Y direction. Sorbent molecule located outside the slab. Water molecules fill the remaining space in the simulation box. The whole system is 3D periodic.			
1.6	Publication						

2. Model equation

	Area	Subarea	Standard metadata	Example	Unit	Version	Literature
2	Model Type and Name			Molecular dynamics with self-adjusted bias (Metadynamics)			
2.1	Model entity		Material	atoms			
			Biopolymers/lipids	n.a.			
			Small entities	atoms			
			Solvent	atoms			
2.2	Model Physics / Chemistry Equation PE's	Equations		drop-down menu			

		Physical quantities for each equation		coordinates, velocities, pairwise potential, biased potential (drop-down menu)			
2.3	Materials relations	MR Equations	Material	user-defined force field			E. G. Brandt, A. P. Lyubartsev, "Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Adsorption of Amino Acid Side Chain Analogues and a Titanium Binding Peptide on the TiO ₂ (100) Surface." J. Phys. Chem. C, 119 (32), 18126-18139, 2015. doi: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b02670.
			Biopolymers/lipids				
			Small entities	General AMBER force field			J. Wang, R. M. Wolf, J. W. Caldwell, P. A. Kollman, D. A. Case, "Development and testing of a general amber force field." Journal of Computational Chemistry, 25, 1157-1174, 2004. doi: 10.1002/jcc.20035.
			Solvent	TIP3P			P. Mark, L. Nilsson, "Structure and Dynamics of the TIP3P, SPC, and

							SPC/E Water Models at 298 K.” J. Phys. Chem. A, 105 (43), 9954–9960, 2001. doi: https://doi.org/10.1021/jp003020w
		Physical quantities / descriptors for each MR	Force field parameters	charge, LJ parameters, bond, angle and dihedral parameters (drop-down)			
			Bias potential	Rate, instantaneous collective variable value as a function of atomic positions which vary in time			
2.4	Simulated input			NVT simulation of equilibrium molecular dynamics structure of overall system			
2.5	Publication						

3. Modelling Metadata

	Area	Subarea	Standard metadata	Example	Unit	Version	Literature
3.1	Numerical Solver		Algorithm	Verlet			
			Ensemble	NVT (canonical)			
			Thermostat	v-rescale			
			Barostat	n.a.			
			Other	Well-tempered metadynamics algorithm with collective variable determined as the surface separation distance between the sorbent			A. Barducci, G. Bussi, M. Parinello, "Well-tempered Metadynamics: A smoothly converging

				molecule and surface			and tunable free-energy method." Phys. Rev. Lett., 100, 020603, 2008. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.100.020603
			Size				
3.2	Software Tool		Numerical integration	Gromacs		2018.6	M. J. Abraham, et al., "GROMACS: High performance molecular simulations through multi-level parallelism from laptops to supercomputers." SoftwareX, 1-2, 19-25, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.softx.2015.06.001
			Parametrisation	Force field parameters: charge, LJ parameters, bond, angle and dihedral parameters (drop-down)			E. G. Brandt, A. P. Lyubartsev, "Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Adsorption of Amino Acid Side Chain Analogues and a Titanium Binding Peptide on the TiO ₂ (100) Surface." J. Phys. Chem. C, 119 (32), 18126-18139,

							2015. doi: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b02670
			Mata-dynamics	Plumed		2-2.5.1	The PLUMED consortium. "Promoting transparency and reproducibility in enhanced molecular simulations." Nat. Methods 16, 670, 2019. doi: 10.1038/s41592-019-0506-8
3.3	Time Step				2 fs		
3.4	Computation Representation	Physics Equation	Equation of motion, classical mechanics (molecular dynamics)	Newton's equation			
			Molecular dynamics sampling method	Well-tempered metadynamics with adaptive Gaussians width			
		Material relations	short-range	pairwise interactions (or more specific: Coulomb, vdW,...)			
			longe-range	Particle Mesh Ewald (PME)			
		Material					
3.5	Computational Boundary Conditions		System	3D			
			Unit cell	any of the seven crystal systems			

			Material	2D slab in X-Y direction			
3.6	Additional Solver Parameters		Total simulation time	~300	ns		
			Pre-equilibration time		1 ns		
			Thermostat relaxation time		1 ps		
			Real-space cutoff		1 nm		
			PME grid spacing		0.1 nm		
			Initial height of Gaussian		2.5 kJ mol ⁻¹		
			Bias factor		15		
			Additional potential	wall for the sorbent at large distance from the surface: $U_{wall}(s)=k(s-a)^4$			
			Additional potential: force constant		40 kJ mol ⁻¹ Ang ⁻⁴		
			Additional potential: Bias		1.5 nm		
3.7	Publication						E. G. Brandt, A. P. Lyubartsev, "Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Adsorption of Amino Acid Side Chain Analogues and a Titanium Binding Peptide on the TiO ₂ (100) Surface." J. Phys. Chem.

4.3	Margin of error		2 KJ/mol				